

The Influence of Commitment, Discipline, and Motivation on Doctors' Performance

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to examine the influence of commitment, discipline, and motivation on doctors' performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang. The study was motivated by the hospital's quality indicators, which show that doctors' compliance with Clinical Practice Guidelines ranges from 75% to 90%, below the 100% target, and outpatient waiting times exceeding the established standards. A quantitative approach was employed using statistical analysis, including linear regression. The population consisted of all 37 doctors working at the hospital, and total sampling was applied. The results indicate that commitment, discipline, and motivation partially contribute 10.4%, 26.4%, and 14% to performance, respectively, with commitment showing a significant effect. Simultaneously, these variables have a positive influence on doctors' performance, explaining 29.6% of the variance, while the remaining 70.4% is influenced by other factors. These findings suggest that strengthening discipline and motivation, along with improving performance evaluation systems, is essential to enhance doctors' performance and support better healthcare service delivery.

I. INTRODUCTION

Doctors' performance is an important issue in improving and sustaining healthcare development in Indonesia. Performance reflects the achievement of strategic and operational activities carried out by individuals or groups within an organization. Performance assessment is a process used to evaluate human resource outcomes through specific performance indicators and evaluation instruments (Ministry of Health of Indonesia, 2009). Clinical Practice Guidelines (CPGs) are guidelines for primary healthcare doctors and constitute an essential part of healthcare service standards. These guidelines serve as references for doctors in delivering quality healthcare services to the community. The implementation of CPGs is expected to improve healthcare quality while reducing unnecessary patient referrals. However, the performance of doctors at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang, still indicates several problems. Based on data obtained from the medical service department, the quality indicator achievement related to internal medicine specialists' compliance with CPGs for diagnoses such as typhoid fever, gastroenteritis, dengue hemorrhagic fever, diabetes mellitus, and pulmonary tuberculosis in adult inpatients only reached an average of 72.2%, which remains below the expected

target (Dewi Sri Hospital Profile, 2017). In addition, outpatient waiting times frequently exceed the standards established by the hospital. These conditions indicate that doctors' performance still requires improvement.

Several factors may influence doctors' performance, including commitment, discipline, and motivation. Organizational commitment is considered an important factor in improving employee performance. Koentjoro (2007) stated that the initial step in building organizational performance is developing commitment and concern among employees within the organization. Previous research conducted by Suryani (2021) also found that organizational commitment significantly influences employee performance in healthcare institutions.

Work discipline is another factor closely related to performance improvement. At Dewi Sri Hospital, work discipline remains relatively low, as several doctors do not begin outpatient services according to the predetermined schedule, resulting in longer patient waiting times. Hasibuan (2016) explained that employees with high discipline demonstrate responsibility, obedience to organizational rules, and compliance with work standards. Previous studies also

reported that work discipline positively affects employee performance (Sya’roni et al., 2018).

In addition to commitment and discipline, motivation plays an important role in encouraging doctors to improve their work performance. Motivation can be defined as an internal drive that directs individuals toward achieving organizational and personal goals. Motivated employees tend to demonstrate greater enthusiasm, responsibility, and persistence in carrying out their duties. A previous study conducted by Yuninda (2017) revealed that motivation significantly affects employee satisfaction and performance among doctors in healthcare organizations. Based on these conditions, this study aims to examine the influence of commitment, discipline, and motivation on doctors’ performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Primary data were obtained directly from respondents, while secondary data were collected from Dewi Sri Hospital through hospital document reviews. The population of this study consisted of doctors working at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang. The inclusion criteria included doctors who had worked at the hospital for at least one year, were willing to participate as research respondents, and were assigned to inpatient services as either general practitioners or specialist doctors. Based on these criteria, 37 doctors out of 67 doctors working at Dewi Sri Hospital were selected as the research sample. Data collection was conducted by distributing questionnaires to respondents through Google Forms. Prior to data collection, the questionnaire instrument was tested for validity and reliability among doctors at Intan Barokah Hospital, Karawang. After the data were collected, the responses were edited and organized into a master table for further statistical analysis. The data were then analyzed using simple linear regression, multiple linear regression, and t-tests (Sugiyono, 2019).

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Commitment at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang

The calculation results presented in the table showed a score of 1831 or 82.5% of the ideal score of 2220. Therefore, the commitment variable was categorized as very high. It can be concluded that, overall, doctors at Dewi Sri Hospital demonstrated a very high level of commitment. Doctors with a high level of commitment tend to devote their thoughts, energy, abilities, and skills to support the future development of the hospital (Koentjoro, 2007).

The commitment variable consisted of three sub-variables, namely affective commitment, continuance commitment, and normative commitment, measured using 12 questionnaire items. Based on the analysis results, the total score for the affective commitment sub-variable was 772 (83.5%) out of the highest possible score of 925. Meanwhile, the continuance commitment sub-variable obtained a score of 601 (81.2%) out of 740, and the normative commitment sub-variable achieved

a score of 458 (82.5%) out of 555. The total overall score for the commitment variable was 1831 (82.5%) out of the ideal score of 2220.

Ideally, the expected score for respondents’ answers to the 12 questionnaire items was 2220. The calculation results indicated that the obtained score reached 1831 or 82.5% of the ideal score. Thus, the commitment variable was categorized as very high, indicating that doctors at Dewi Sri Hospital generally possessed a strong organizational commitment.

B. Discipline at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang

The discipline variable consisted of four sub-variables, namely compliance with time regulations, compliance with organizational regulations, compliance with work behavior, and compliance with other organizational rules, measured using five questionnaire items.

Respondents’ responses regarding discipline at Dewi Sri Hospital showed that the total score for the discipline variable was 794 (85.8%) out of the highest possible score of 925. Ideally, the expected score for respondents’ answers to the five questionnaire items was 925. The calculation results indicated that the obtained score reached 794 or 85.5% of the ideal score. Therefore, the discipline variable was categorized as very high. It can be concluded that doctors at Dewi Sri Hospital generally demonstrated a very high level of work discipline. High work discipline reflects employees’ responsibility and compliance with organizational regulations (Hasibuan, 2016).

C. Discipline at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang

The motivation variable consisted of five sub-variables, namely physiological needs, social needs, safety needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization, measured using six questionnaire items. Respondents’ responses regarding motivation at Dewi Sri Hospital showed that the total score for the motivation variable was 924 (83.3%) out of the highest possible score of 1110.

Ideally, the expected score for respondents’ answers to the six questionnaire items was 1110. The calculation results showed that the obtained score reached 924 or 83.3% of the ideal score. Therefore, the motivation variable was categorized as very high. It can be concluded that doctors at Dewi Sri Hospital generally had a very high level of motivation. Motivation plays an important role in encouraging employees to improve their work performance and achieve organizational goals (Robbins, 2018).

D. Doctors’ Performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang

Respondents’ responses regarding the performance variable indicated that doctors’ performance was represented by ten sub-variables, namely assessment, supporting examinations, consultation, diagnosis, education and discharge planning, monitoring and evaluation, treatment/intervention, consultation, monitoring, and evaluation. These indicators were measured using 12 questionnaire items. Based on the analysis results, the total

score for the performance variable was 1822 (82.10%) out of the highest possible score of 2220.

Ideally, the expected score for respondents’ answers to the 12 questionnaire items was 2220. The calculation results indicated that the obtained score reached 1822 or 82.10% of the ideal score. Therefore, the performance variable was categorized as very high. It can be concluded that doctors at Dewi Sri Hospital generally demonstrated a very high level of performance in providing healthcare services.

E. The Influence of Commitment on Doctors’ Performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang

To examine the influence of commitment on doctors’ performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang, a simple linear regression analysis was conducted. The results of the regression analysis are presented in Table I.

Table I. The influence of commitment on doctors’ performance at dewi sri hospital, karawang

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardize d Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std Error	Beta		
Constatnta	27,653	10,722	0,323	2,579	0,014
Komitmen	0,436	0,216		2,017	0,051

Table I presents the results of the simple linear regression analysis examining the influence of commitment on doctors’ performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang. The analysis showed that commitment had a regression coefficient of 0.436, indicating a moderate positive influence on doctors’ performance.

Based on the analysis results, the calculated t-value for the commitment variable was 2.017. This value was compared with the t-table value at a significance level of 0.05 and degrees of freedom (df = 34), resulting in a t-table value ranging from -1.691 to 1.691. Since the calculated t-value (2.017) was outside the acceptance range of the t-table values, the null hypothesis (H0) was rejected and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) was accepted. This finding indicates that commitment had a significant influence on doctors’ performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang.

The regression equation demonstrated that every one-point increase in the commitment rating would increase doctors’ performance by 0.436 points. In addition, the correlation coefficient obtained was 0.323 with a positive direction, indicating that commitment and doctors’ performance had a positive linear relationship. This finding suggests that higher organizational commitment among doctors tends to improve their performance in providing healthcare services (Koentjoro, 2007).

Table II. The correlation and determination analysis of commitment on doctors’ performance

Mode	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0,323	0,104	0,079	4,01817

Based on Table 2, the correlation coefficient (R) was 0.323 and showed a positive relationship between commitment and doctors’ performance. The coefficient of determination analysis indicated that the R Square value was 0.104, meaning that commitment contributed 10.4% to explaining the variance in doctors’ performance, while the remaining 89.6% was influenced by other variables not examined in this study. These findings are consistent with previous studies reporting that organizational commitment plays an important role in improving employee performance within healthcare organizations (Suryani, 2021).

F. The Influence of Commitment on Doctors’ Performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang

To measure the influence of discipline on doctors’ performance, simple linear regression analysis, correlation analysis, coefficient of determination analysis, and t-tests were conducted. The results of the simple linear regression analysis are presented in Table III.

Table III. Simple linear regression analysis of discipline on doctors’ performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std Error	Beta		
Constatnta	27,637	6,683	0,514	3,836	0,000
Disiplin	1.106	0,312		3,547	0,001

The analysis results showed that discipline had a regression coefficient of 0.514, indicating a moderate positive influence on doctors’ performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang. Based on Table 3, the calculated t-value for the discipline variable was 3.547. This value was compared with the t-table value at a significance level of 0.05 and degrees of freedom (df = 34), resulting in a t-table range of -1.691 to 1.691. Since the calculated t-value (3.547) was outside the acceptance range of the t-table values, the null hypothesis (H0) was rejected and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) was accepted. This finding indicates that discipline had a significant influence on doctors’ performance.

Table IV. Correlation and determination analysis of discipline on doctors’ performance

Mode	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.514 ^a	0.264	0.243	3.64122

Based on Table 4, the correlation coefficient (R) was 0.514 and showed a positive relationship between discipline and doctors’ performance. This finding indicates that higher levels of work discipline are associated with better doctors’ performance. The coefficient of determination analysis showed that the R Square value was 0.264, indicating that discipline contributed 26.4% to explaining the variance in doctors’ performance, while the remaining 73.6% was influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

These findings suggest that work discipline plays an important role in improving doctors’ performance. Doctors who comply with organizational regulations, work schedules, and professional standards tend to demonstrate better performance in delivering healthcare services. This result is consistent with previous studies indicating that work discipline positively affects employee performance (Hasibuan, 2016; Sya’roni et al., 2018).

G. The The Influence of Commitment on Doctors’ Performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang

To measure the influence of motivation on doctors’ performance, simple linear regression analysis, correlation analysis, coefficient of determination analysis, and t-tests were conducted. The results of the simple linear regression analysis are presented in Table V.

Table V. Simple linear regression analysis of motivation on doctors’ performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std Error	Beta		
Constatnta	28,074	8,889	0,374	3,158	0,003
Motivasi	0,848	0,355		2,388	0,022

The analysis results indicated that motivation had a regression coefficient of 0.374, showing a moderate positive influence on doctors’ performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang. Based on Table V, the calculated t-value for the motivation variable was 2.388. This value was compared with the t-table value at a significance level of 0.05 and degrees of freedom (df = 34), resulting in a t-table range of -1.691 to 1.691. Since the calculated t-value (2.388) was outside the acceptance range of the t-table values, the null hypothesis (H0) was rejected and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) was accepted. Therefore, motivation had a significant influence on doctors’ performance.

The motivation variable contributed 37.4% to explaining the variance in doctors’ performance, while the remaining 63.6% was influenced by other variables not examined in this study. These findings indicate that motivation plays an important role in improving doctors’ work performance. Doctors with higher motivation levels tend to demonstrate greater responsibility, enthusiasm, and persistence in providing healthcare services. This finding is consistent with previous studies suggesting that work motivation positively affects employee performance (Robbins, 2018; Rahma et al., 2013).

H. The Simultaneous Influence of Commitment, Discipline, and Motivation on Doctors’ Performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang

Multiple linear regression analysis was conducted to examine the simultaneous influence of commitment, discipline, and motivation on doctors’ performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang. The results of the multiple linear regression analysis are presented in Table VI.

Table VI. Multiple linear regression analysis of commitment, discipline, and motivation on doctors’ performance

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig
	B	Std Error	Beta		
Constatnta	16,893	11,069		1,526	0,136
Komitmen	0,057	0,235	0,042	0,244	0,808
Disiplin	0,891	0,385	0,414	2,316	0,027
Motivasi	0,420	0,370	0,186	1,136	0,264

Based on Table VI, the calculated t-value for the commitment variable was 0.244. This value was compared with the t-table value at a significance level of 0.05 and degrees of freedom (df = 34), resulting in a t-table range of -1.691 to 1.691. Since the calculated t-value for commitment (0.244) fell within the acceptance range of the t-table values, the null hypothesis (H0) was accepted and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) was rejected. Therefore, commitment did not have a significant influence on doctors’ performance in the simultaneous regression model.

Meanwhile, the calculated t-value for the discipline variable was 2.316, which exceeded the t-table range. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H0) was rejected and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) was accepted, indicating that discipline had a significant influence on doctors’ performance. Furthermore, the calculated t-value for the motivation variable was 1.136, which fell within the t-table range. Thus, the null hypothesis (H0) was accepted and the alternative hypothesis (Ha) was rejected, indicating that motivation did not have a significant influence on doctors’ performance in the simultaneous model.

Table VII. Simultaneous Hypothesis Testing (F-Test) of Commitment, Discipline, and Motivation on Doctors’ Performance

<i>Model</i>	<i>Sum of Square</i>	<i>df</i>	<i>Mean Square</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Sig</i>
Regression	186,809	3	62,270	4,628	0,008
Residual	444.002	33	13.455		
Total	630.811	36			

The simultaneous F-test results showed that the calculated F-value was 4.628. This value was compared with the F-table value at a significance level of 0.05 with $df_1 = 2$ and $df_2 = 35$, resulting in an F-table value of 3.267. Since the calculated F-value (4.628) was greater than the F-table value (3.267), it can be concluded that commitment, discipline, and motivation simultaneously had a significant influence on doctors’ performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang.

Table VIII. Correlation and determination analysis of commitment, discipline, and motivation on doctors’ performance

<i>Mode</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R Square</i>	<i>Adjusted R Square</i>	<i>Std. Error of the Estimate</i>
1	0.514 ^a	0.296	0.232	3.66805

Based on Table 8, the correlation coefficient (R) was 0.544 and showed a positive relationship between commitment, discipline, motivation, and doctors’ performance. This finding indicates that the independent variables simultaneously had a positive and linear relationship with doctors’ performance. The coefficient of determination analysis showed that the R Square value was 0.296, indicating that commitment, discipline, and motivation together contributed 29.6% to explaining the variance in doctors’ performance, while the remaining 70.4% was influenced by other variables not examined in this study. These findings suggest that discipline was the strongest predictor among the independent variables in influencing doctors’ performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang.

I. The Influence of Commitment on Doctors’ Performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang

Commitment and doctors’ performance showed a positive relationship, as indicated by the R Square value of 0.104. This finding demonstrates that the commitment variable contributed 10.4% to explaining the variance in doctors’ performance, while the remaining 89.6% was influenced by other variables not examined in this study. These findings are consistent with previous research conducted by Qamaruddin et al. (2021), which reported an R² value of 0.112 or 11.2%. The study explained that organizational commitment contributed 11.2% to employee performance in the Tourism and Labor Departments of Palopo City.

Commitment is closely related to employee performance. Harnoto (2006) stated that employees with low organizational commitment tend to be indifferent and lack responsibility toward the organization. In contrast, employees with strong commitment demonstrate pride, responsibility, and enthusiasm in carrying out their duties, which ultimately improves organizational performance. Therefore, an increase in organizational commitment is expected to enhance employee performance.

Organizational commitment can also be viewed as a condition in which employees support organizational goals and choose to remain within the organization. High organizational commitment reflects employees’ loyalty and alignment with organizational objectives (Iriana et al., 2004). Previous studies have consistently shown that work commitment significantly affects work outcomes, employee performance, attendance levels, and job satisfaction.

J. The Influence of Discipline on Doctors’ Performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang

The results showed that the correlation coefficient (R) between discipline and performance was 0.514, indicating a positive relationship between the two variables. The coefficient of determination analysis showed an R Square value of 0.264, meaning that discipline contributed 26.4% to explaining the variance in doctors’ performance, while the remaining 73.6% was explained by other variables. The t-test analysis also demonstrated that discipline had a significant influence on doctors’ performance.

These findings are in line with the study conducted by Pangarso and Susanti (2016), which found that work discipline positively affected employee performance at the Basic Social Services Bureau of the West Java Provincial Secretariat. Their study indicated that an increase in work discipline significantly improved employee performance. Similarly, Sanjaya (2015) reported that work discipline had a positive and significant effect on employee performance with a regression coefficient of 0.340 ($p < 0.05$).

Good work discipline reflects employees’ sense of responsibility toward their assigned duties. Discipline encourages improvements in employee performance and supports the achievement of organizational goals. In other words, work discipline is one of the main factors determining employee performance. Indicators of work discipline include obedience to organizational regulations, punctuality, compliance with work procedures, and personal awareness in carrying out responsibilities (Sanjaya, 2015). Employees with good discipline tend to demonstrate better performance, whereas poor discipline may lead to lower performance outcomes.

K. The Influence of Motivation on Doctors’ Performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang

The analysis results showed that motivation had a significant influence on doctors’ performance. The motivation variable contributed 37.4% to explaining the

variance in performance, while the remaining 63.6% was influenced by other factors not examined in this study. Therefore, other variables such as age, education level, years of service, and gender should also be considered in future studies examining employee performance.

These findings are consistent with previous studies conducted by Rahma et al. (2013) at Ulin Regional Hospital, Banjarmasin, which found that both intrinsic and extrinsic motivation had a positive and significant effect on doctors’ performance. Similarly, Sanjaya (2015) reported that work motivation positively and significantly influenced employee performance with a regression coefficient of 0.363 ($p < 0.05$). According to Mathis and Jackson (2012), motivation is an internal desire that drives individuals to perform certain actions. Furthermore, Hasibuan, as cited in Sutrisno (2019), explained that motivation is a stimulus that encourages individuals’ willingness to work in order to achieve specific goals. Robbins, as cited in Irviani and Fauzi (2018), also stated that motivation is a process involving intensity, direction, and persistence in achieving organizational goals. Therefore, highly motivated doctors are more likely to demonstrate better performance in delivering healthcare services.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of this study, several conclusions can be drawn. Doctors at Dewi Sri Hospital demonstrated a high level of organizational commitment. This finding indicates that doctors possessed strong affective and normative commitment, reflected in their sense of belonging to the hospital, willingness to defend the institution, pride in the hospital, and willingness to participate in hospital activities. In addition, doctors demonstrated high levels of loyalty, professionalism, and compatibility with the organization.

The level of work discipline among doctors at Dewi Sri Hospital was also categorized as high. This condition was reflected in punctuality, compliance with hospital regulations, adherence to professional behavior, and ethical conduct in implementing medical codes of ethics within the hospital environment. Doctors at Dewi Sri Hospital also demonstrated a high level of motivation. This finding was reflected in respondents’ questionnaire scores related to social needs, safety needs, esteem needs, and self-actualization, while physiological needs were categorized at a moderate level.

The performance of doctors at Dewi Sri Hospital in providing healthcare services was categorized as high. Doctors were able to work professionally across various performance dimensions, including assessment, diagnosis, consultation, intervention, monitoring, evaluation, and discharge planning. This condition may be influenced by the fact that most doctors were specialists and had more than ten years of work experience. However, supporting examinations still showed relatively moderate performance levels.

Partially, commitment contributed 10.4% to explaining the variance in doctors’ performance and had a significant positive influence on performance. Discipline contributed 26.4% and also demonstrated a significant positive influence on doctors’ performance. Motivation contributed 14.0% and similarly showed a positive influence on performance. These findings indicate that improvements in commitment, discipline, and motivation are associated with improvements in doctors’ performance at Dewi Sri Hospital, Karawang.

Simultaneously, commitment, discipline, and motivation had a positive and significant influence on doctors’ performance. The coefficient of determination analysis showed an R Square value of 0.296, indicating that these three variables collectively contributed 29.6% to explaining doctors’ performance, while the remaining 70.4% was influenced by other variables not examined in this study.

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